

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF WRESTLING IN THE EDUCATION OF YOUTH

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada kurashning yoshlar tarbiyasidagi o'rni, u orqali shakllanadigan axloqiy, psixologik va jismoniy xususiyatlar tahlil qilingan. Unda yoshlarni sog'lom turmush tarziga jalb etish, ularni kurash mashg'ulotlari orqali irodali, intizomli va maqsadga intiluvchan shaxs sifatida shakllantirishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari yoritilgan.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье анализируется роль борьбы в воспитании молодежи, нравственные, психологические и физические характеристики, формируемые через нее. В ней подчеркиваются педагогические возможности вовлечения молодежи в здоровый образ жизни и формирования их как волевых, дисциплинированных и целеустремленных личностей посредством тренировок по борьбе.

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the role of wrestling in the education of young people, the moral, psychological and physical characteristics formed through it. It highlights the pedagogical opportunities for involving young people in a healthy lifestyle and shaping them as strong-

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kurash, yoshlar tarbiyasi, sport psixologiyasi, axloqiy fazilatlar, sog'lom turmush tarzi, pedagogika.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

борьба, воспитание молодежи, спортивная психология, нравственные качества, здоровый образ жизни, педагогика.

KEYWORDS

wrestling, youth education, sports psychology, moral qualities, healthy lifestyle, pedagogy.

willed, disciplined and goal-oriented individuals through wrestling training.

As one of the national sports, wrestling is not only a means of physical culture, but also a powerful factor in upbringing, socialization and psychological formation. Through wrestling, young people not only become strong, but also become self-controlled, patient, respectful, and proud. Especially today, the role of wrestling in forming a healthy lifestyle and educating the younger generation on the basis of national pride is incomparable.

Wrestling is one of the ancient sports of Uzbekistan, which is not only a sport, but also a symbol of national culture and sports traditions. The national sport of wrestling, which is one of the national values of our people, serves to introduce the Uzbek heritage to the whole world. In particular, during the years of independence, extensive work was carried out to further develop wrestling and increase its prestige. In turn, a number of decrees and resolutions of the President of Uzbekistan and the government serve as a program for the appearance of wrestling in the world arenas.

The material evidence found as a result of the research, studies, archaeological scientific searches and observations conducted by historians proves that the age of Kurash is at least 2.5-3 thousand years. Unique finds and examples of fine art carved on rocks, discovered in the oases of Surkhan and Zarafshan, as well as in a number of ancient settlements in the Fergana Valley, fully testify to this.

The strongest wrestlers became famous among the people, and legends began to be woven about them. Pahlavon Mahmud, who lived in the 12th century, is a vivid example of this. His grave is still a favorite place for pilgrims and one of the holy places. The name of Pahlavon Mahmud from Khorezm is forever etched in history. One of the great leaders of the Futuvvat-juvonmardlik group. He wrote in Persian. He was engaged in post-indozi, telpakdozi. He was never defeated in competitions throughout his life. Pahlavon Mahmud traveled to many countries, visited Iran, India and many other Eastern countries, traveled throughout Central Asia and fought with strong wrestlers everywhere. But nowhere, neither in his homeland nor in foreign lands, did his back touch the ground. Pahlavan Mahmud was not only a wrestler, but also a poet, thinker, and a well-rounded person. He embodied high moral qualities, humanity, and physical perfection.

In the 14th century, Amir Temur, an unparalleled commander and statesman who left a bright mark on human history, used wrestling to train his soldiers and improve their physical fitness. It is known that Amir Temur's army was considered the most powerful and invincible army of his time.

Abu Ali ibn Sina also emphasized in his book "The Canons of Medicine" that wrestling plays a special role in a person's mental and physical condition. According to the great physician, a person who regularly engages in physical training will not need treatment for illness.

Wrestling training develops an athlete not only physically, but also spiritually. The following are positive qualities that are formed at a young age through wrestling: respect and discipline, patience, responsibility, honesty, etc.

Wrestling is not only a sport that requires physical strength and skill, but also a socio-educational tool that plays an important role in the moral and spiritual upbringing of the younger generation. Since ancient times, it has been recognized not only as a martial art, but also as a means of forming such qualities as patriotism, loyalty, endurance, and honesty.

First of all, young people involved in wrestling learn such qualities as self-improvement, discipline, respect for the coach, and fairness and honesty towards their opponents. Each wrestling session requires internal discipline, patience, and willpower from the participant. This teaches young people to be responsible not only in sports, but also in everyday life.

In wrestling, honesty and decency are more important than winning. Respect for the opponent, adherence to the rules and ethical standards during the fight are the moral foundations of this sport. Especially in our national wrestling - Uzbek wrestling - there are values such as helping the opponent after he is knocked down, paying tribute to him. This directs the wrestlers to humanity and high moral qualities.

Wrestling also strengthens the feelings of patriotism in the younger generation. Many wrestlers' training and competitions are held under the national anthem and flag. This serves to strengthen loyalty to the country.

The educational significance of wrestling can be seen in the following areas:

Moral education: honesty, justice, respect, patience.

Willpower education: the ability to overcome oneself, strengthening the will.

Aesthetic education: training the body, striving for beauty.

Patriotic education: loyalty to the country, a sense of pride and honor.

Social education: teamwork, mutual respect, friendship.

Wrestling is not only an important tool for ensuring the healthy physical development of young people, but also an important tool for forming their spiritual and moral integrity. Therefore, it is necessary to widely introduce wrestling in the preschool, school and higher education systems, making it an integral part of the educational process.

Wrestling is a powerful tool that is inextricably linked to school, family and society, and provides personal development for young people. It is observed that the

psychological state of young people involved in wrestling is stronger than others. The reasons for this are as follows: stress resistance, willpower, self-confidence, motivation. Wrestling is one of the most effective sports that strengthens the mental health of young people. Sports psychology is a scientific field that studies the mental state of athletes, factors that affect their mental activity and behavior. Especially in sports that require strength, speed, endurance and strategic thinking, such as wrestling, psychological preparation is as important as physical preparation.

The role of psychological factors in wrestling.

During the wrestling process, the athlete not only fights against the opponent, but also confronts internal states such as fear, excitement, and insecurity that arise in him. The stress and psychological pressure that arise before the competition directly affect the athlete's technical and tactical actions. Therefore, psychological preparation of athletes is one of the necessary conditions.

Basic psychological qualities.

Wrestling athletes must have the following psychological qualities:

Willpower: the ability to continue fighting despite pain, fatigue, and failure during the fight.

Attention and concentration: the ability to sense the opponent's movements and make decisions quickly.

Emotional stability: the ability to manage stress, anger, and excitement.

Motivation: the desire to achieve success, inner morale.

Self-confidence: belief in one's own abilities, and the ability to act without fear of the opponent.

Psychological preparation methods.

The following methods are used to improve the psychological preparation of wrestlers:

Visualization: the athlete imagines the fight in advance, thereby creating psychological preparation for it.

Autotraining: saying positive words to oneself, motivating oneself through thoughts.

Breathing exercises: reducing nervousness, keeping the heart rate normal.

Motivational conversations before training: improving the athlete's mental state by talking with a coach or psychologist.

The coach plays an important role not only in the physical but also in the mental preparation of the athlete. He must identify the athlete's strengths and weaknesses and provide psychological support based on an individual approach. There must be an individual motivational approach for each athlete.

Success in wrestling depends not only on physical strength and technique, but also on the state of mind. Psychological preparation is the strengthening of the athlete's inner world, the formation of skills to overcome stress and fear, and self-control. Therefore, comprehensive preparation of wrestling athletes - physical, technical, tactical and psychological - is an important condition in modern sports.

Regularly engaging in wrestling plays a special role in strengthening the health of young people:

- Strengthens the cardiovascular system
- Proper development of the musculoskeletal system
- Strengthens immunity
- Prevents excess weight, stress, and physical weakness.

Young people who engage in wrestling become more active in social life, behave more freely. A healthy lifestyle is the main factor ensuring the physical, mental and social health of a person. Sport, and in particular wrestling, plays an important role in shaping this lifestyle. Wrestling is not only a sport, but also a means of developing a person's health, spiritual well-being and a positive attitude towards life.

The impact of wrestling on a healthy lifestyle.

Wrestling has a complex effect on the human body.

Strengthening physical health: Wrestling exercises move the whole body, strengthen the muscles, cardiovascular, respiratory and nervous systems.

Increasing immunity: Regular wrestling increases the body's ability to fight diseases.

Preventing overweight: Wrestling exercises require high energy expenditure, which prevents the accumulation of excess fat.

Mental health and wrestling; wrestling is also an effective tool in forming a healthy psychological state,

Reducing stress and nervousness: During training, negative energy is released, which relieves a person mentally.

Increase self-confidence: Through success in wrestling, an athlete develops a positive attitude and confidence in themselves.

Discipline and willpower: Wrestling develops positive psychological qualities such as determination, patience, and self-control.

Socially healthy lifestyle.

Wrestling encourages people to be socially active and live in a healthy environment.

Protecting youth from negative influences: Young people involved in wrestling stay away from harmful street habits.

Teamwork skills: Athletes train in a friendly environment, which strengthens human relationships.

Striving for a healthy life: Proper nutrition, regular sleep, work and rest are important for wrestlers.

Wrestling is a sport that develops a healthy body, strong will and a strong spirit. It teaches a person to live with activity, discipline, and the desire for a healthy life. Therefore, it is important to popularize wrestling as an integral part of a healthy lifestyle and widely introduce it into the lives of young people.

Wrestling training serves as the following pedagogical tool for teachers-trainers:

- Teaches students-youth to work in a team
- Forms hard work, determination
- Encourages action through a competitive environment
- Develops leadership qualities
- Helps to think independently and make decisions.

Therefore, it is important to establish wrestling classes as educational activities. Wrestling is not just a physical activity, but also a powerful tool for shaping young people into well-rounded individuals. Wrestling allows for the harmonious formation of moral, psychological, physical and social qualities in the younger generation. Therefore, the role of wrestling in the modern system of upbringing and education needs to be strengthened.

REFERENCES

1. Niyozov N. “Fundamentals of Sports Psychology”. Tashkent, 2020.
2. Hasanov M. “Kurash and Education”. Tashkent, 2021.
3. “Youth and Sport” magazine, 2023, No. 3.
4. Karimov B. “National sports and moral qualities in youth”. Samarkand, 2022.
5. Mirzayev D. “Social effectiveness of pedagogical sports training”. Tashkent, 2019.